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THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF GREEN FINANCING IN FORMING A GREEN ECONOMY

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TSUE independent researcher

Abstract: The directions aimed at the sustainable development of the "green" economy in the country through "green" financing are becoming an integral part of the global trend. The international financial system is developing towards the active growth of the "green" sector and responsible investments in global market finance. The investment paradigm itself is changing, more and more attention is being paid to transformative investments that have the potential not only to achieve a certain economic result, but also to have a positive social and environmental impact. The purpose of this article is to fully identify the general prospects and directions of the development of "green" finance and its theoretical aspects. This goal was achieved using systematic analysis methods, induction, graphical methods, as well as the study of systematic literature. The theoretical foundations of the concept of "green" finance are studied. The content of "green" financial instruments and institutions, their strengths and weaknesses are identified. Green financial instruments are intended not only to obtain economic benefits from their use, but also to protect the environment, solve ecological and climate problems.

Key words: green economy, green finance, low carbon economy, environmentally responsible investment, green green bonds, green economy, greening the financial system, green technology.

Annotatsiya: Mamlakatda "yashil" moliyalashtirish orqali "yashil" iqtisodiyotni barqaror rivojlantirishga qaratilgan yo'nalishlar global tendensiyaning ajralmas qismiga aylanib bormoqda. Xalqaro moliya tizimi "yashil" sektorning faol o'sishi va global bozor moliyasida mas'uliyatli investitsiyalar tomon rivojlanmoqda. Investitsiya paradigmasi o'zgarib, iqtisodiy natijani emas, balki ijobiy ijtimoiy va ekologik ta'sirni ta'minlay oladigan transformatsion investitsiyalarga tobora ko'proq e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi "yashil" moliyalashtirishning umumiy istiqbollari va nazariy jihatlarini to'liq aniqlashdan iborat. Ushbu maqsad tizimli tahlil, induksiya, grafik usullar va tizimli adabiyotlarni o'rganish orqali amalga oshirildi. "Yashil" moliyalashtirish konsepsiyasining nazariy asoslari o'rganilib, "yashil" moliyaviy instrumentlar va institutlarning mazmuni, ularning kuchli va zaif tomonlari aniqlangan. "Yashil" moliyaviy instrumentlardan foydalanish nafaqat iqtisodiy foyda olish, balki atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish, ekologik va iqlim muammolarini hal etish uchun ham mo'ljallangan.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil iqtisodiyot, yashil moliya, past uglerodli iqtisodiyot, ekologik mas'ul investitsiya, yashil obligatsiyalar, moliya tizimini "yashillashtirish", yashil texnologiyalar.

Аннотация: Направления, ориентированные на устойчивое развитие «зеленой» экономики через «зеленое» финансирование, становятся неотъемлемой частью глобального тренда. Международная финансовая система развивается в сторону активного роста «зеленого» сектора и ответственных инвестиций на глобальном финансовом рынке. Инвестиционная парадигма меняется, всё большее внимание уделяется трансформационным инвестициям, которые способны не только обеспечить экономический результат, но и оказать положительное социальное и экологическое воздействие. Цель статьи заключается в полном выявлении общих перспектив и направлений развития «зеленого» финансирования и его теоретических аспектов. Эта цель достигнута с использованием методов системного анализа, индукции, графических методов, а также изучения систематической литературы. Изучены теоретические основы концепции «зеленого» финансирования. Определены содержание, сильные и слабые стороны «зеленых» финансовых инструментов и институтов. «Зеленые» финансовые инструменты предназначены не только для получения экономической выгоды, но и для защиты окружающей среды, решения экологических и климатических проблем.

Ключевые слова: зеленая экономика, зеленое финансирование, низкоуглеродная экономика, экологически ответственное инвестирование, зеленые облигации, озеленение финансовой системы, зеленые технологии.

INTRODUCTION

World renewable energy systems located in or powered by the oceans are expected to make a significant contribution to the green energy transition in the coming decades. Offshore wind and its renewable energy sector are expected to account for 31 percent of global energy consumption, with global value added increasing from US\$38 million in 2000 to US\$5 billion in 2020, and the global offshore wind market is estimated to be worth over US\$39.6 billion in 2024 and is projected to exceed US\$146 billion by 2031.[1] Countries around the world are committing to deploying offshore wind energy systems that will power 1.5 billion homes per year by 2050. [2] For this reason, The energy crisis in the world economy, geopolitical instability, environmental degradation, and the steady decline of natural resources have had a significant impact on the pace of global economic development in recent years. This, in turn, has led to the need to finance the efficiency of countries' economies through financing the green economy. special attention is being paid to the improvement of mechanisms.

In the new stage of reforms in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to «transition to the use of «green» technologies in economic sectors, in particular, resource-saving, waste-free production, technologies that allow for waste processing, and safe chemicals, as well as to study the possibilities of using renewable energy technologies and put them into practice.»[3] and in this area, special attention is paid to the issues of “widespread implementation of green economy principles, sustainable financing of projects aimed at adapting the economy to climate change” [4]. However, despite the positive results achieved in recent years as a result of the reforms carried out in our country in the formation of a green economy, the issue of increasing economic efficiency due to the problems of the process of reaching different levels of resources in the effective use of existing green investment projects in sectors and industries of the economy, financing, remains one of the most pressing problems. Therefore, the tasks of actively attracting green investments to sectors and industries of the economy and forming sources of new green investment projects, as well as creating an added value chain through the wide use of the opportunities of green technologies in increasing economic efficiency have become one of the most pressing problems today.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The first studies in this direction were reflected in the scientific works of T. Malthus and D. Ricardo. Research conducted prior to the emergence of the idea of a “green economy” mainly focused on the growing problems associated with the use of limited and non-renewable natural resources, environmental pollution and degradation, as well as the disruption of natural biological processes. To prevent environmental pollution, the terms “green economy” and “green finance” appeared during the 1980s–2000s.

In the scientific works of R. Solow and V. Leontiev, the concepts of sustainable development and economic growth were advanced, while mathematical and economic modeling was actively applied to analyze the interrelation between the economy and the environment [5].

Although foreign economists have provided numerous definitions of green finance, the number of definitions proposed by domestic researchers remains limited. The term “green finance” was first introduced in 1992 by Richard Sandor while teaching at Columbia University, where he provided an authorial definition of the concept. According to R. Sandor, green finance should be viewed as a core mechanism for promoting sustainable and environmentally responsible economic growth, primarily through prioritizing investments that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate climate change [6].

According to S. Khosla and other foreign economists, green financing sources are directed toward projects and initiatives focused on sustainable development, the production of environmentally friendly goods, industrial pollution and wastewater treatment, biodiversity protection, and the mitigation of climate change impacts [7].

The scientific team led by U. Walz defines green finance as encompassing all forms of investment and lending that generate positive environmental impacts and promote ecological sustainability [8]. Similarly, M. Ghoul conceptualizes green finance as a link that connects the financial industry, environmental protection, and economic growth [9].

Building on the results of extensive research, N. Lindenberg defines green finance as “a set of green investments, state policies, and the financial systems associated with them” [10].

Among local economists, A. Vakhobov and Sh. Khajibakiev define green finance as “all forms of investment and lending that take into account factors influencing the environment and ensure ecological sustainability” [11]. According to S. Pulatova, green finance represents investments that generate environmental benefits and, more broadly, contribute to the development of ecological sustainability. It aims to redirect financial flows from banks, microcredit institutions, insurance organizations, and investment companies to the public, private, and non-profit sectors in pursuit of sustainable economic development [12].

Meanwhile, Chinese economists Chi-Chuan Li and Chien-Chiang Li emphasize that, based on their research, there is no universally accepted definition of green finance as a new and evolving financial system [13].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, data were obtained from reports of international organizations (World Bank, OECD, UNDP), national legislative documents, and scientific publications to examine the theoretical foundations of green financing. The collected information was analyzed using systematic analysis, comparative, inductive, and deductive approaches to develop scientific conclusions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Since environmental protection measures cannot be implemented without financial resources, there is a need to create a "Green Financing" system. Therefore, CIS economists K.G. Bunkevich and T.A. Gorbacheva put forward the concepts of "Green Finance" and "Green Investment" in their scientific research. They put forward the idea that the use of "green financial instruments" is intended not only for economic gain and profit, but also for solving environmental and climate problems. [14] Foreign economists D. Zhang, M. Mohsin, A.K. Rasheed, Y. Chang conducted practical analyses of green economic efficiency, the Durbin model, the efficiency and role of clean energy in the green economy, and green economy indicators[15]. Similarly, our country's economists Z. Nurov and M.Kh. Rajabova studied the current state of investments in the energy sector of the «Green Economy» in the world economy and its development trends. [16] Another group of our domestic economists studied foreign experiences of the transition to a «Green Economy» and some aspects of issues such as economic and environmental problems in industrial development.

According to local economist A.A. Isajanov, "green" growth means stimulating economic growth and development, in which natural assets are preserved, resources and ecosystem services are provided continuously. Our well-being depends on them. To do this, green growth should stimulate and widely use investments and innovations that ensure sustainable development and lead to the emergence of new economic opportunities[17]. Another local economist, N.N. Oblomurovov, draws attention to the role and importance of international carbon markets in "green" financing. International carbon markets play an important role in economically efficient global greenhouse gas emissions reduction. The number of carbon emission trading systems is increasing around the world. In addition to the European Union carbon trading system, national or regional trading systems have been established and are operating in Canada, China, Japan, New Zealand, South Korea, Switzerland and the USA[18]. In this regard, the project of our country's access to international carbon markets in cooperation with the World Bank is also noteworthy. With the support of an innovative project of the World Bank, Uzbekistan is trying to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and access international carbon markets. The grant provided within the framework of the project in the amount of 46 million 250 thousand US dollars will be directed to stimulating measures within the framework of energy subsidy reform. In particular, the project will allow Uzbekistan to collect «carbon credits» and sell them on international carbon markets. This project is the first such international initiative in Uzbekistan and Central Asia within the framework of the Paris Agreement, allowing the country to access carbon markets[19].

In the concept of the financing mechanism of the green economy, our author's research aims to show the differences in the content and structure of the «green» financing mechanism from the traditional financial mechanism and to justify the need to introduce new, additional elements into it. The studied scientific and published economic literature contains many definitions of the financial mechanism. All of them can be distinguished from each other in two respects. The first is the degree of formation and use of the financial mechanism: at the national or macro level and at the enterprise level. It should be noted that in this study, the mechanism for building and financing a green economy in increasing the efficiency of economic sectors was studied at the global, national and, to a lesser extent, corporate levels. In the second aspect, the financial mechanism as a set of elements is its application methods, tools, levers, regulatory and legal support, information and methodological support. It is this set of elements that the authors traditionally include in the financial mechanism. Our present study suggests a much more extensive set of improved elements beyond the above. Since the content of these elements is known and clear from many scientific sources, we will move on to the financing mechanism of the green economy, which has a number of differences below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Traditional financial mechanism

All of the above traditional elements will have a “green” color and a corresponding “green” purpose and composition. At the same time, for individual elements, it will be enough to add a simple “green” phrase, which will distinguish it from its traditional counterpart (for example, “green” credit, “green” bonds, “green” investments and “green” projects, etc.). However, the green economy financing mechanism will include new elements that are not present in the traditional mechanism, since without them the green economy financing mechanism will not have the full-fledged character necessary for a “green” economy.

Financial instruments are a set of actions that are used in each financial system to ensure that economic outcomes are aligned with environmental objectives. These include, as well as government regulation, key instruments such as exchange rates, interest rates, pricing strategies, and others. For example, exchange rates have a significant impact on international trade and investment flows, and their manipulation can either encourage or discourage environmentally sustainable practices.

Interest rates are a powerful lever that directly affects borrowing costs and investment decisions, and determines the direction of economic activity towards green initiatives. Pricing instruments play a crucial role in reflecting the true environmental costs of production, goods and services, and in shaping consumption patterns that contribute to sustainable economic development (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Green economy financing mechanism

Financial instruments also operate in financial markets to generate financial assets and financial liabilities that are intended to promote green investments and sustainable economic development initiatives. Instruments that include securities, currencies, loans, and others are specifically designed to support environmentally friendly initiatives. For example, green bonds provide financing for projects that have a positive impact on the environment, such as renewable energy infrastructure or sustainable agriculture initiatives. [20] Similarly, green funds pool investments from a variety of sources to finance environmentally friendly projects or companies (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Financial sources of the green economy financing mechanism

Figure 3 presents the sources of «green» financing for green financing. Focusing on the picture, financial resources are divided into two categories: internal and external. Internal resources are formed by public sector organizations, the private sector operating in the country, as well as public-private partnership models. External resources are attracted through foreign private sector and international cooperation schemes and programs.

The search for sources of financing, investors willing to invest in high-risk, low-carbon projects with a long-term payback period, the development of innovative financial schemes for cooperation between participants, the creation of new financial products and other areas will be the basis for ensuring success in the energy transition and resource exploration for Central Asia in developing countries in general.

Based on the above analysis, green financing refers to the use by the state of funds from the state budget, the private sector, and international organizations, as well as financial resources raised through financial markets or using various financial instruments, to finance green initiative activities and projects aimed at increasing the efficiency of economic sectors, in order to protect the environment and achieve sustainable economic development in the interests of the socio-economic development of society.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it can be said that in the current reality, environmental problems and problems associated with climate change cannot be ignored, which are of great importance on a national and international scale and concern almost every inhabitant of our planet. One of the important directions for improving the environment

of human society is, of course, the transition to a «green» economy. In implementing this transition, it will be necessary to use «green» financial instruments. However, such global transitions are always accompanied by many problems that require their own solutions on an international and national scale. It is impossible to implement environmental protection measures without appropriate financing. Therefore, there is a need to create a separate «green» financing system, and in this regard, it is necessary to improve the theoretical aspects and methodological foundations of the «green» economy, «green» finance, «green» investments. «Green» financial instruments are intended not only to obtain economic benefits from their use, but also to solve environmental and climate problems while preserving the environment.

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